

Crop management

Environmental limitations to rice cultivation in the Punjab

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Five sites representing typical rice-growing areas of the Punjab were selected to evaluate suitability for rice production. On the basis of soil-site

characteristics (see table), four suitability classes have been defined, from highly suitable to currently not suitable.

Average rice yields under controlled conditions with fertilizer (50-12-12 kg NPK/ha) based on soil test suggest that the yield data correlate well with soil-site suitability class.

The yield potential of rice soils in the Punjab is controlled by rainfall during growing season, soil texture, drainage, infiltration, soil reaction, and soluble salts. It is possible to make yield predictions at different levels of the suitability class on the basis of soil-site

characteristics and their degree of limitation. The study predicts the following environmental limitations for sustained rice cultivation:

- Rainfall—less than 300 mm during growing season Jul-Sep is limiting.
- Soil type—fine loamy surface and subsurface texture with more than 16% clay.
- Drainage—optimum from moderately well to imperfectly drained.
- Soil reaction—optimum pH 7-8.3.
- Soluble salts—salinity and alkalinity are the primary obstacles. □

Soil and site suitability characteristics and their limitations.^a Ludhiana, India.

Soil	Rainfall (mm) Jul-Sep (annual)	Water intake (mm) cumulative 6h	Drainage	pH	ECe 10 ⁻³ dS/m	Exchangeable sodium percentage	Silt	Clay	Organic C (%)	Overall limitation	Land suitability class ^b	Yield (t/ha)	
												Control	Recommended fertilizer based on soil-test ^c
Rawalpindi clay loam (Aquic Ustochrepts)	202 (315)	29	Imperfect	8.6 (8.4)	1.6 (1.7)	15.6 (9.3)	41.5 (33.0)	30.0 (34.1)	0.45 (0.22)	1-2	S2	3.7	6.1
Degree of limitation	2	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0				
Samana sandy loam (Udic Ustochrepts)	474 (680)	58	Well	7.4 (7.6)	1.0 (0.7)	6.9 (6.6)	18.8 (29.9)	12.7 (15.7)	0.35 (0.17)	2-3	S3	2.8	5.1
Degree of limitation	0	3	3	0	0	0	2	2	1				
Bhoewal loam (Typic Haplustalfs)	532 (713)	42	Moderately well	7.4 (8.2)	1.0 (0.8)	7.4 (8.2)	50.3 (48.8)	25.9 (29.2)	0.72 (0.26)	0-1	S1	4.6	7.8
Degree of limitation	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Narrike sandy loam (Natraqic Calciorthid)	290 (425)	40	Moderately well	9.4 (9.3)	2.4 (3.6)	40 (43)	20.6 (29.7)	18.2 (22.8)	0.17 (0.12)	3-4	S4	1.2	1.7
Degree of limitation	2	1	1	4	3	4	0	1	2				
Gurdaspur loam (Udic Haplustalfs)	603 (88.6)	48	Moderately well	7.2 (7.3)	0.4 (0.4)	2.5 (1.1)	30.6 (40.7)	10.4 (15.7)	0.59 (0.29)	1-2	S1-2	4.1	7.4
Degree of limitation	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				

^aValues in brackets indicate weighted mean of the column. ^bS1 = highly suitable, S4 = currently not suitable. ^cAverage of 5 yr.

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Effect of farmyard manure (FYM) supplemented with N, P, K on grain yield

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FYM is an important source of plant

nutrients for irrigated rice in Bhutan. In the Wangdiphodrang-Punakha valley, FYM is predominantly composed of animal manures mixed with rice straw in various stages of decomposition. An estimated average of 7 t FYM (fresh weight)/ha is applied before transplanting. The actual rate varies widely, from zero to 20 t/ha.

As fertilizer-responsive rice varieties become more widespread, FYM

probably will continue to contribute significantly to crop nutrition and soil condition.

We supplemented FYM with N, P, K to evaluate its effect on grain yield of IR36. IR36 seedlings raised in dry bed nurseries were transplanted in mid-Jun at 49 d after seeding with 20- × 20-cm spacing in 4- × 6-m banded plots, in a completely randomized block design with 7 treatments and 3 replications.

The soil was a loam with pH 6.6, 1.2% organic C, 9.3 meq CEC/100 g, 4.6 ppm available P (Olsen's), 0.332 meq